

Applying Machine Learning Models to Identify key Determinants of Bankruptcy Risk: Evidence from Vietnamese Real Estate Firms

Nguyen Mai Chi¹, Tran Thi Ngoc Anh², Trinh Thi Huyen Dieu³, Nguyen Thu Ha⁴, Vu Thi Thu Huong⁵

^{1,2,3,5}Faculty of Mathematical Economics, Thuongmai University, Hanoi, Vietnam.

⁴Faculty of Finance and Banking, Thuongmai University, Hanoi, Vietnam,

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ABSTRACT

This study applies machine learning classification models to predict bankruptcy risk among real estate firms in Vietnam, particularly in the context of heightened market volatility and elevated credit risk during the period 2019–2023. Using firm-level financial data and macroeconomic variables obtained from the National Statistics Office, the authors develop and compare the predictive performance of several algorithms, including LightGBM, XGBoost, Random Forest, and Decision Tree, against the traditional Logistic Regression model. The empirical results indicate that boosting techniques, specifically LightGBM and XGBoost, outperform other approaches in terms of predictive accuracy and overall performance metrics. SHAP analysis reveals that the ratio of shareholders' equity to total liabilities is the most influential predictor of bankruptcy risk. In addition, asset utilization efficiency and capital structure exert significant effects on financial distress probability. Profitability indicators and cash flow generation capacity further confirm their essential role in maintaining financial stability. While institutional and macroeconomic factors exhibit certain effects, their influence is not dominant relative to firm-specific financial characteristics. Overall, the findings suggest that bankruptcy risk in the real estate sector primarily stems from firms' internal financial structure and operational efficiency rather than external macroeconomic conditions.

Corresponding Author:
Vu Thi Thu Huong

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INTRODUCTION

Bankruptcy risk represents one of the most severe financial risks faced by firms, reflecting the likelihood that a company becomes insolvent and is unable to continue normal operations. In periods of economic volatility and tightening financial conditions, bankruptcy risk tends to intensify, particularly in capital-intensive and cyclical industries such as real estate. The consequences of bankruptcy risk extend beyond the firm itself, resulting in operational disruption, insolvency, restructuring, or market exit, and also affect creditors, investors, employees, and the broader market through contagion effects, declining confidence, and liquidity fluctuations. Given the sector's heavy reliance on financial leverage and sales-generated cash flows, credit and interest rate shocks can rapidly erode the financial health of real estate firms. The crisis period of 2022–2023 accelerated structural adjustments within the real estate sector. A substantial number of firms exited the market, while many others were compelled to restructure

debt or suspend and delay project implementation. Following this downturn, the period 2024–2025 has shown signs of recovery, marked by a significant increase in firms resuming operations and a rebound in profitability among listed companies. These developments underscore the urgent need for reliable bankruptcy risk prediction tools to support timely decision-making by managers, investors, financial institutions, and regulators. Bankruptcy risk assessment methods have been widely studied and applied worldwide. Among them, Altman's Z-score model (1968) remains one of the most prominent approaches (Bandyopadhyay, 2006). Logistic regression has also been extensively employed for bankruptcy prediction, particularly useful when nonlinear relationships exist among financial variables (Ohlson, 1980). In recent years, machine learning techniques have emerged as a powerful alternative in bankruptcy forecasting due to their ability to process large and complex datasets without strict distributional assumptions. Machine learning models such as Random Forest, XGBoost, Support Vector

Machines, and Artificial Neural Networks are capable of learning from historical patterns and delivering improved classification accuracy in identifying financially distressed firms (Barboza et al., 2017; Nguyen et al., 2023; Orlando & Michael, 2024; Park et al., 2021). Machine learning models can automatically optimize and adapt to new data, thereby enhancing predictive performance over time. Empirical evidence from Barboza et al. (2017) and Shetty et al. (2022) indicates that machine learning approaches significantly outperform traditional statistical methods such as discriminant analysis and logistic regression in bankruptcy prediction. In Vietnam, in-depth research on bankruptcy forecasting remains limited, particularly studies focusing on the real estate sector. Moreover, there is a scarcity of research employing machine learning techniques combined with SHAP (Shapley Additive Explanations) to interpret the key determinants of bankruptcy risk within an emerging market context. This study aims to contribute to the literature by applying machine learning classification techniques to identify the most important determinants of bankruptcy risk among Vietnamese real estate firms, thereby providing new empirical evidence and methodological insights for bankruptcy risk assessment in emerging markets.

THEORETICAL FOUNDATIONS

Bankruptcy and Bankruptcy Risk

According to Tirole (2006), bankruptcy reflects a situation in which a firm is unable to meet its debt obligations as they fall due, thereby facing the risk of liquidation or restructuring. This process generates social costs due to the reallocation of resources within the economy. From a corporate finance perspective, Brealey, Myers, and Allen (2017) argue that bankruptcy is not merely a legal event but an economic condition in which the market value of a firm's assets is insufficient to cover its total liabilities. This situation gives rise to bankruptcy costs, including direct costs (legal and administrative expenses) and indirect costs (loss of reputation, business disruption, and deterioration of customer relationships).

Under the 2014 Law on Bankruptcy of Vietnam, bankruptcy is defined as the status of an enterprise or cooperative that becomes insolvent and is declared bankrupt by a People's Court. Insolvency is defined as the failure to fulfill debt obligations within three months from the due date. Although the definitions differ in emphasis, bankruptcy is generally viewed as a severe state of financial distress accompanied by a specific legal procedure to resolve it. The core objective of bankruptcy law is to establish a fair framework for resolving claims between debtors and creditors while maintaining market order. The primary legal premise is the inability to repay debts when due. Karels and Prakash (1987) provided an in-depth analysis of the nature of bankruptcy risk, arguing that bankruptcy is a process that

begins with financial distress and concludes with legal resolution. They emphasized that financial failure is a necessary but not sufficient condition for bankruptcy.

Rescher (1982), as well as Merna and Al-Thani (2008), define risk as the possibility of adverse future events. Accordingly, bankruptcy risk can be understood as the likelihood that a firm becomes unable to meet its financial obligations, leading to operational disruption and threatening its survival.

Measurement of Bankruptcy Risk

This study measures bankruptcy risk through the probability of bankruptcy estimated using the Ohlson (1980) model. The bankruptcy probability function P , where $0 \leq P \leq 1$, is expressed through the logistic function:

$$p_i = Pr(\text{Risk} = 1) = (1 + \exp(-y_i))^{-1} \quad (1)$$

where

$$y_i = \sum_j \beta_j X_{ij} = \beta' X_i$$

X_i is the vector of explanatory variables for observation i , and β is the vector of unknown parameters. The probability p increases with y , where $y = \ln\left(\frac{P}{1-P}\right)$.

The specific model is defined as follows:

$$Y = -1.32 - 0.407(\text{SIZE}) + 6.03(\text{TLTA}) - 1.43(\text{WCTA}) + 0.0757(\text{CLCA}) - 1.72(\text{OENEG}) - 2.37(\text{NITA}) - 1.83(\text{FUTL}) + 0.285(\text{INTWO}) - 0.521(\text{CHIN}) \quad (2)$$

where:

SIZE = $\log(\text{Total Assets})$,

TLTA = Total Liabilities / Total Assets,

WCTA = Working Capital / Total Assets,

CLCA = Current Liabilities / Current Assets,

OENEG = 1 if Total Liabilities exceed Total Assets (otherwise 0),

NITA = Net Income / Total Assets,

FUTL = Funds from Operations (EBITDA) / Total Liabilities,

INTWO = 1 if net income is negative for two consecutive years (otherwise 0),

CHIN = $(NI_t - NI_{t-1}) / (|NI_t| + |NI_{t-1}|)$, where NI_t is net income in the most recent period.

The output value of Equation (2) is the log-odds ratio (Y). A more negative Y corresponds to a lower probability of bankruptcy. To obtain the bankruptcy probability, Y is transformed into a probability value between 0 and 1 using Equation (1).

Machine Learning Classification Algorithms

Logistic Regression Logistic Regression is a statistical method used to model a binary dependent variable (0/1) through the logit function, thereby estimating the probability of an event occurring based on linear combinations of explanatory variables. Its main advantages include

conceptual simplicity, ease of interpreting coefficients, and relatively low computational complexity. The model facilitates a clear understanding of the marginal effects of individual predictors. However, logistic regression has several limitations. It assumes a linear relationship in the logit space, its predictive performance may deteriorate when the underlying relationships are nonlinear or when the data contain substantial noise, and it is sensitive to multicollinearity among explanatory variables. In practice, logistic regression is commonly employed as a baseline model in bankruptcy prediction studies (Altman, 1968; Ohlson, 1980) and serves as a benchmark for comparison with more advanced machine learning techniques. In the context of this research, logistic regression provides a reference framework for evaluating and improving more sophisticated models applied to real estate data in Vietnam.

Decision Tree A Decision Tree is a classification model based on a tree structure in which data are recursively partitioned at each node according to criteria such as Gini impurity or entropy, with the objective of predicting bankruptcy probability. The main advantages of decision trees include interpretability, rule-based transparency, the absence of linearity assumptions, and the ability to handle mixed types of variables. However, the model is prone to overfitting if tree complexity is not properly controlled and may exhibit instability when small changes occur in the dataset. In bankruptcy prediction, decision trees are frequently applied to binary classification problems and also serve as foundational components for ensemble methods. Within this study, decision trees are particularly suitable for real estate data characterized by heterogeneous financial and macroeconomic features, and they support the development of ensemble models that help mitigate class imbalance issues in the Vietnamese context.

Ensemble Techniques

Random Forest

Random Forest is an ensemble learning technique based on bagging, combining multiple independent decision trees trained on randomly sampled subsets of data. Final predictions are typically determined through majority voting. This aggregation mechanism enhances predictive accuracy and robustness against noise and outliers, while also providing estimates of feature importance. Compared to a single decision tree, Random Forest generally reduces the risk of overfitting. Nevertheless, the method entails relatively high computational costs, longer training time as dataset size increases, and lower interpretability compared to a single tree. In bankruptcy prediction tasks, Random Forest often achieves strong classification performance (e.g., high AUC) and is particularly useful in the presence of imbalanced financial data. For Vietnamese real estate firms, Random Forest can effectively identify key financial

indicators, such as leverage and liquidity, and often outperforms logistic regression in empirical applications.

XGBoost XGBoost (Extreme Gradient Boosting) is a boosting algorithm that sequentially builds weak decision trees, where each subsequent tree corrects the errors of its predecessors. The model incorporates regularization mechanisms to mitigate overfitting. Due to its strong capacity for modeling nonlinear relationships and handling imbalanced data, XGBoost often delivers superior predictive performance. It also provides feature importance measures and supports parallel computation, thereby improving training efficiency in empirical applications. However, the model is relatively sensitive to hyperparameter selection and may overfit if not properly tuned. In bankruptcy prediction, XGBoost typically achieves high classification accuracy and can be combined with interpretability techniques such as SHAP to enhance transparency. In the context of Vietnamese real estate data, XGBoost is well suited to capturing market volatility, such as high leverage and low liquidity during the 2022–2023 period, and has the potential to outperform baseline models when applied to large-scale firm-level datasets.

LightGBM LightGBM (Light Gradient Boosting Machine) is a boosting framework designed to optimize training speed and scalability, particularly suitable for large datasets with high-dimensional features. By employing a leaf-wise tree growth strategy, LightGBM achieves fast computation and high predictive performance. It also performs effectively in imbalanced data settings, especially when combined with feature selection techniques such as Recursive Feature Elimination (RFE). However, the model requires careful hyperparameter tuning and may exhibit instability when the dataset contains substantial noise. Previous studies on default and bankruptcy prediction have shown that LightGBM can achieve very high accuracy (approximately 98.7% when combined with RFE), demonstrating its strong potential in risk classification tasks. For Vietnamese real estate data, LightGBM is particularly appropriate for panel data analysis and can incorporate sector-specific variables to optimize predictive performance while aligning model outputs with market dynamics.

Performance Evaluation Metrics for Classification Models

The confusion matrix is a widely used tool for evaluating the performance of classification models, applicable to both binary and multi-class classification. Tharwat (2021) defines the confusion matrix as a tabular representation comparing a model’s predicted outcomes with the actual values of the dataset. According to Kulkarni et al. (2020), it is a common metric that reflects the number of correct and incorrect predictions. A confusion matrix consists of four main components: True Positive (TP), False Positive (FP), True Negative (TN), and False Negative (FN).

Table 1. Confusion Matrix

	Actual	High Bankruptcy Risk	Low Bankruptcy Risk
Predicted			
High Bankruptcy Risk (Positive)		TP	FP
Low Bankruptcy Risk (Negative)		FN	TN

Source: Compiled by the authors

According to Lessmann et al. (2015), accuracy measures the overall effectiveness of a model and is calculated as follows:

$$Accuracy = \frac{TP + TN}{TP + TN + FP + FN}$$

Kulkarni et al. (2020) and Tharwat (2021) caution that accuracy can be misleading when applied to imbalanced datasets. A model may achieve high accuracy while delivering poor predictive performance. To address this limitation, other metrics such as recall and specificity are commonly used. These are defined as follows:

$$Recall = \frac{TP}{TP + FN}$$

$$Specificity = \frac{TN}{TN + FP}$$

Tharwat (2021) emphasizes that these two metrics are less sensitive to class imbalance because they are calculated based on separate columns of the confusion matrix, unlike accuracy, which depends on all four components.

Regarding precision, Kulkarni et al. (2020) define it as a measure reflecting the correctness of predictions labeled as “positive.” It is calculated as:

$$Precision = \frac{TP}{TP + FP}$$

Unlike recall and specificity, precision is highly sensitive to class imbalance.

The F1-score is a composite metric that combines precision and recall. It evaluates the balance between correctness (precision) and coverage (recall) of a model. The F1-score ranges from 0 to 1, with higher values indicating better classification performance.

$$F_1 = 2 \times \frac{Precision \times Recall}{Precision + Recall}$$

Receiver Operating Characteristic (ROC) and the Area Under the Curve (ROC-AUC) are commonly used standards for evaluating classification models. Tharwat (2021) describes the ROC curve as a two-dimensional graph where the vertical axis represents the True Positive Rate (TPR, or recall) and the horizontal axis represents the False Positive Rate (FPR). The ROC curve illustrates the trade-off between benefits (True Positives) and costs (False Positives). Lessmann et al. (2015) define AUC as the probability that a randomly selected positive case will receive a higher predicted score than a randomly selected negative case. The AUC value ranges from 0 to 1 and is calculated by summing the areas of trapezoids under the

ROC curve. One major advantage of ROC-AUC is its robustness to imbalanced datasets.

Application of Explainable AI to Identify Important Features

Lundberg and Lee (2017) introduced SHAP (SHapley Additive exPlanations) as a unified framework for interpreting machine learning model predictions. This approach is grounded in cooperative game theory, in which Shapley values are used to fairly allocate the total payoff among players according to their contributions. Nohara et al. (2019) explain that SHAP represents the output of a specific prediction as the sum of the contributions of each feature, similar to coefficients in a linear model. Specifically, Lundberg and Lee (2017) define SHAP as belonging to the class of additive feature attribution methods and demonstrate that it is the only solution satisfying three desirable properties simultaneously: local accuracy, missingness, and consistency. Regarding implementation, Nguyen et al. (2023) describe that the Shapley value for a feature is computed by evaluating the difference between the model’s prediction with and without that feature, averaged over all possible subsets of the remaining features. For tree-based models (such as Random Forest and Gradient Boosting), Moen (2020) and Lundberg et al. (2020) propose TreeSHAP, an optimized method that enables faster and more accurate computation of SHAP values. Nohara et al. (2019) also suggest a technical enhancement by using the variance of SHAP values (L2 norm) instead of the sum of absolute values (L1 norm) to measure variable importance, thereby improving consistency with linear models.

In practical applications, SHAP provides interpretability at both global and local levels. Nguyen et al. (2023) indicate that the global importance of a feature can be assessed by calculating the mean absolute Shapley value across the entire dataset. Moreover, visualization tools such as the SHAP summary plot and SHAP dependence plot allow researchers to identify nonlinear relationships and the direction of impact (positive or negative) of each feature on prediction outcomes.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Data

This study uses annual enterprise survey data collected and published by the General Statistics Office of Vietnam for the period 2019–2023. From this enterprise survey dataset, we extracted 139,335 firms operating in the real estate sector,

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classified at the five-digit industry level according to the VSIC 2018 industrial classification system of Vietnam.

The variables were constructed from financial indicators provided in the enterprise survey data. In addition, several macroeconomic variables from reliable sources were incorporated.

Variables

The probability of bankruptcy (P) is measured using the O-score model developed by Ohlson (1980).

The dependent variable, bankruptcy risk (Risk), is a binary variable that takes the value of 1 when the estimated probability $P \geq 0.5$, indicating high bankruptcy risk, and 0 when $P < 0.5$, representing low bankruptcy risk firms.

The explanatory variables used in the research model are described in detail in Table 2.

Table 2. Features

Name	Variable Formula	Description
Asset Structure Variables		
R01	Used Capital / Fixed Assets	Measures financial structure, indicating the ratio of used capital to fixed assets.
R02	Equity / Used Capital × 100	Reflects the proportion of equity in total used capital, indicating financial autonomy.
R03	Financial Debt / Used Capital × 100	Measures financial leverage, reflecting the extent of debt usage in operations.
R04	Equity / Total Assets × 100	Measures capital safety, indicating the proportion of assets owned by the firm.
Liquidity and Solvency		
R05	Working Capital Requirement / Current Assets	Reflects the ability of short-term assets to meet operational needs.
R06	Current Assets / Short-term Liabilities	Measures the ability to meet short-term obligations.
R07	Financial Debt / Operating Cash Flow	Indicates the time required for operating cash flow to fully repay debt.
Operating Profitability Variables		
R08	Cash Flow / Total Revenue × 100	Reflects the percentage of revenue that generates actual cash inflows.
R09	Working Capital Requirement / Total Revenue × 360	Indicates the number of revenue days required to cover working capital needs.
R10	Net Working Capital / Total Revenue × 360	Measures the number of operating days that net working capital can be converted into revenue.
R11	Total Revenue / Tangible and Intangible Assets	Measures asset utilization efficiency—how much revenue one unit of assets generates.
R12	Total Revenue / Total Assets	Measures overall asset efficiency.
R13	EBIT / Operating Revenue × 100	Represents operating profit margin, reflecting profitability from core business activities before interest and taxes.
R14	Value Added / Total Revenue × 100	Measures the proportion of value created relative to total revenue.
R15	Operating Cash Flow / Value Added × 100	Reflects the ability to convert value added into actual cash flow.
R16	Profit or Loss Before Tax / Operating Revenue × 100	Measures pre-tax profit margin, reflecting overall profitability including financial activities.
R17	Profit or Loss / Equity × 100	Measures return on equity, indicating capital efficiency.
R18	Profit or Loss / Used Capital × 100	Measures return on capital employed.
Inventory and Turnover Variables		
R19	Inventory / Total Revenue × 360	Measures inventory days, reflecting inventory turnover speed.
R20	Accounts Receivable / Operating Revenue × 360	Measures receivable days, reflecting the firm’s credit policy.
R21	Accounts Payable / Operating Revenue × 360	Measures payable days, reflecting cash flow management efficiency.

Contribution of Expense Components		
R22	Labor Cost / Value Added × 100	Represents the proportion of labor cost in value added, reflecting labor efficiency.
R23	Taxes / Value Added × 100	Measures tax burden relative to value added.
R24	Interest Expense/Value Added × 100	Measures interest burden relative to value added.
Variables from Altman’s Z-Score Model (1968)		
P1	Working Capital / Total Assets	Measures the proportion of working capital in total assets, reflecting financial flexibility.
P2	Retained Earnings / Total Assets	Reflects the firm’s ability to accumulate profits for reinvestment.
P3	EBIT / Total Assets	Measures return on assets, indicating efficiency in generating profits from assets.
P4	Equity / Total Liabilities	Reflects firm value relative to total debt obligations.
Macroeconomic Variables		
GNI	Gross National Income	Gross National Income at constant 2010 prices, representing macroeconomic conditions and overall income levels affecting real estate demand and cash flows.
PCI	Provincial Competitiveness Index	Represents provincial institutional quality and business environment, potentially affecting project implementation, legal risk, and operational efficiency. Source: VCCI. https://pcivietnam.vn/en
COVID	COVID-19	Measures the impact of the COVID-19 pandemic shock on the market and firm operations.

Source: Authors’ literature review and compilation

Procedure for Building Supervised Classification Models

The research model is designed by integrating firm-level financial indicators and macroeconomic variables to predict bankruptcy risk as a binary classification problem. Specifically, the mathematical model is defined as:

$$Risk = f(X)$$

where: *Risk* is a binary dependent variable measuring bankruptcy risk based on the O-score model of Ohlson (1980). *X* is a vector of explanatory features described in Table 2. *f(X)* represents a nonlinear function estimated using classification algorithms, including a baseline model (Logistic Regression), tree-based models (Decision Tree, Random Forest), and boosting models (XGBoost, LightGBM).

These models are selected due to their ability to handle imbalanced data (the proportion of high bankruptcy risk firms is typically below 20%) and capture nonlinear relationships, thereby outperforming the traditional logistic regression model (Nguyen et al., 2023).

The classification modeling procedure consists of the following steps:

Step 1: Data Preparation

Data collection, Data cleaning, Data standardization, Splitting the dataset into training and testing sets, with an 80%–20% ratio, ensuring stratification based on the dependent variable

Step 2: Model Selection and Training

Step 3: Model Performance Comparison

Step 4: Model Interpretation using SHAP to identify important features

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Data Preparation

Data collection: The dataset includes real estate firms in Vietnam during the 2019–2023 period, obtained from the annual enterprise survey conducted by the National Statistics Office (NSO) of Vietnam. Data cleaning: The original dataset contained 139,335 observations. After removing observations with missing values in the selected features, the cleaned dataset consisted of 14,522 firms. Missing values were not imputed in order to preserve the integrity of the original data. Data standardization: Independent variables were standardized using StandardScaler, transforming them to a common scale with a mean of 0 and a standard deviation of 1. Data splitting: The dataset was divided into a training set (11,617 observations) and a testing set (2,905 observations), following an 80%–20% split while maintaining stratification based on the dependent variable.

Model Training and Selection

Based on the standardized dataset, classification regression models (Lasso Logistic Regression) and tree-based models (Decision Tree, Random Forest, XGBoost, and LightGBM) were trained and evaluated.

Comparison of Performance Metrics

Table 3. Model Performance Comparison

Model	Accuracy	Recall (Sensitivity)	Specificity	F1-Score	AUC-ROC
LightGBM	0.9697	0.8632	0.9843	0.8732	0.9913
XGBoost	0.9670	0.8348	0.9851	0.8592	0.9892
Random Forest	0.9583	0.7578	0.9859	0.8147	0.9847
Decision Tree	0.9356	0.7521	0.9608	0.7385	0.8565
Lasso Logistic	0.8906	0.1283	0.9953	0.2206	0.9009

Source: Model performance report generated from Python

The LightGBM model demonstrates outstanding classification capability, with high performance metrics, particularly an AUC-ROC value close to 1, indicating excellent discrimination between classes.

Identification of Important Features

The classification models compared include Lasso Logistic Regression, Decision Tree, Random Forest, XGBoost, and LightGBM. Among them, LightGBM achieved the best performance based on the evaluation metrics (Table 3).

Subsequently, SHAP was applied to determine feature importance, illustrated through SHAP summary plots (bar plot and beeswarm plot), which highlight the variables exerting the greatest influence on LightGBM’s predictions. SHAP analysis enables the identification of both the magnitude and direction of each variable’s impact on bankruptcy probability. The features are ranked according to the mean absolute SHAP values, reflecting their global importance.

Figure 1. Important Features in the LightGBM Model by SHAP

(1) Market Valuation and Capital Structure - P4 (Equity / Total Liabilities) exhibits the largest and most widely dispersed SHAP values. Red points (high values) are concentrated on the negative SHAP side, indicating that a higher P4 reduces the predicted probability of bankruptcy, whereas lower values (blue points) significantly increase risk. This finding is consistent with Altman’s (1968) Z-

Score model, which emphasizes the role of market-based equity value. Recent machine learning studies on bankruptcy prediction (Barboza et al., 2017) also suggest that market valuation variables often possess strong discriminative power in boosting models. Real estate firms are characterized by long business cycles, high leverage, and strong dependence on market expectations. When equity

declines sharply relative to total debt, the probability of insolvency rises rapidly. Therefore, this variable serves as an important early warning indicator. - R04 (Equity / Total Assets) also shows a significant impact. A low R04 ratio corresponds to positive SHAP values, increasing bankruptcy probability. This reinforces the conclusion that capital structure is a fundamental determinant of financial resilience. The result aligns with the Trade-off Theory of capital structure and empirical evidence from emerging markets (Shumway, 2001). Real estate firms with low equity ratios tend to rely heavily on debt financing, making them more vulnerable during market downturns. When the market freezes and sales cash flows slow, these firms face heightened liquidity risk. Hence, capital structure constitutes a foundational determinant of bankruptcy risk. (2) Asset Utilization Efficiency Two variables, R11 (Revenue / Tangible & Intangible Assets) and R12 (Revenue / Total Assets), rank among the most important features, exhibiting large and stable SHAP dispersion. Low values of these variables increase the probability of bankruptcy, indicating that asset utilization efficiency is a decisive factor in a capital-intensive industry such as real estate.

Given that real estate firms typically hold high-value assets, operate with long project development cycles, and recognize revenue based on project progress, insufficient revenue generation from assets can result in large project inventories, weak cash flows, and increasing debt repayment pressure. This finding is consistent with Ohlson (1980) and recent machine learning studies showing that asset turnover variables significantly improve the predictive accuracy of nonlinear models. The result further confirms that asset turnover plays a central role in the survival capacity of real estate firms in emerging markets. (3) Liquidity and Working Capital Management The group of variables R02, R01, R21, R09, and R05 shows moderate but consistent influence. R02 (Equity / Used Capital) reflects financial autonomy. Lower values of R02 increase bankruptcy risk. R01 (Used Capital / Fixed Assets) reflects capital safety. Lower R01 values increase bankruptcy probability. Variables such as R21 (Payable Days), R09 (Revenue Days Financing Working Capital), and R05 (Working Capital Requirement / Current Assets) also have a significant impact on bankruptcy probability. An extended cash conversion cycle and excessive reliance on trade credit increase liquidity risk. This reflects common practice in Vietnam, where many firms rely on accounts payable and customer advances to finance project development. (4) Profitability and Internal Accumulation Capacity Variables P2, R17, R13, and P3 represent profitability and internal capital accumulation capacity. Low values of these variables substantially increase bankruptcy risk, while higher values reduce bankruptcy probability—though with a smaller magnitude of impact compared to leverage-related variables. This result aligns with the Z-Score model and empirical studies

showing that profits and retained earnings enhance financial resilience. However, in capital-intensive sectors such as real estate, leverage and liquidity constraints exert a stronger influence than short-term profitability. Notably, cash flow variables such as R08 (Cash Flow / Revenue) and R15 (Operating Cash Flow / Value Added) also exhibit significant effects. This highlights that in the real estate sector, accounting profits alone are insufficient to ensure financial safety if actual cash flows are weak. (5) Macroeconomic Variable (PCI) The PCI variable has a measurable but significantly smaller impact compared to internal financial variables. This suggests that bankruptcy risk primarily stems from financial structure and corporate governance efficiency rather than the local institutional environment. However, during periods of strong market volatility, macroeconomic factors may become more influential and warrant further investigation. The application of SHAP helps interpret the “black box” nature of the LightGBM model, enabling a clearer understanding of the most important features and how they influence predictions. This provides a foundation for more detailed data collection and for prioritizing critical variables in future research.

CONCLUSIONS

This study applies tree-based machine learning models and ensemble techniques, combined with SHAP analysis, to identify key determinants of bankruptcy risk among Vietnamese real estate firms. Empirical results indicate that bankruptcy risk is most strongly influenced by financial leverage and market-based capital buffers relative to debt (P4, R04), followed by asset utilization efficiency (R11, R12) and financial autonomy and liquidity indicators (R02, R21, R05). SHAP analysis from the LightGBM model confirms the nonlinear and asymmetric effects of these variables: when equity relative to debt or asset efficiency declines below certain thresholds, bankruptcy probability increases sharply. This reflects the structural characteristics of the real estate industry, capital-intensive operations, long project cycles, and heavy dependence on credit. Bankruptcy in this sector does not merely result from declining profits but primarily from capital structure imbalance and cash flow pressure when assets become illiquid.

Theoretical Contributions

First, the study reinforces and extends classical bankruptcy prediction models (Altman, 1968; Ohlson, 1980) within the context of emerging markets and the real estate sector. Second, the findings emphasize the superior role of market valuation variables (P4) compared to purely accounting-based indicators, contributing empirical evidence on the necessity of integrating market and financial information in bankruptcy risk assessment. Third, the study clarifies the industry-specific characteristics of real estate firms, where asset efficiency and capital structure play more critical roles than short-term profitability measures.

Methodological Contributions

First, the study simultaneously applies multiple machine learning models (Lasso, Decision Tree, Random Forest, XGBoost, LightGBM), enhancing robustness and comparative reliability. Second, the use of SHAP addresses the “black box” limitation of boosting algorithms by clarifying the direction and magnitude of variable effects on bankruptcy risk. Third, the integration of traditional financial indicators, the O-Score framework, and macroeconomic variables establishes a comprehensive analytical framework suitable for the Vietnamese real estate context.

Practical Implications

Real estate managers should prioritize leverage control, maintain safe equity ratios, enhance asset turnover efficiency, and accelerate project progress to improve cash flows. Investors and credit institutions should focus on early warning indicators such as P4, R04, and R11, rather than relying solely on accounting profits. The ML–SHAP framework can be applied as an early warning risk detection tool. Policymakers should strengthen credit supervision and improve capital market transparency to mitigate systemic risk in the real estate sector. Overall, the study not only identifies key determinants of bankruptcy risk in the real estate industry but also contributes theoretically, practically, and methodologically by integrating traditional financial models with modern machine learning techniques, thereby providing a scientific foundation for the development of early warning systems for corporate risk.

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